

**THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE GUIDE-
TRANSLATOR IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM**

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Abstract. This article reveals the role and importance of the guide-interpreter specialty in the field of tourism, as well as the innovative way of conducting the market of guide-interpreter services in the effective development of tourist areas.

Key words. Tourism, guide interpreter, innovative development, tourist area, services market, competition.

Currently, the growth of the processes of innovative development of the market of tourist services in tourism is considered as a necessary element of the development and transformation of economic systems in the conditions of scientific and technical development, as well as the main resource that provides competitive advantage.

The ability of tourist enterprises to timely pay attention to new technological changes in various fields of innovative development of the market of tourist guide-interpreter services related to tourism, to create new methods of work and to improve the results of activities is recognized as a necessary condition for the survival of tourist enterprises. . The need to introduce innovative development of the tourist guide-interpreter services market in tourism encourages competition and a number of other market requirements. Their availability is also related to consumer demands and consumer desires, due to changes in the mentality of a modern person, changes in the demographic, economic and social order.

In the current conditions, a modern specialist cannot continue his activity without using the results of innovative processes in the field of tourist guide-interpreter services market, because the flow of scientific and technical information is growing rapidly, in

this condition, a young specialist, guide-interpreter, scientific should be able to select technical innovations and innovative ideas from information, such ability cannot be achieved without scientific research and creative skills.

People who love tourism visit all corners of our vast planet. It is impossible to know all languages on earth, and some cannot learn international English. There is no point in looking at the sights without learning about their history. If you don't know the local language, an English guide-interpreter will help you in this situation. This is a guide who organizes and conducts tours for one person or a group of people in a foreign country where the native language of the tourists is spoken.

This profession has become very popular in a short time, as people have a desire to travel and travel abroad. The professional duties of a guide-interpreter differ from a regular guide, as he accompanies the tourist during the trip and talks about the sights for several hours.

Currently, the guide-interpreter provides the following services to tourists:

- the guide meets the tourist or a group of people at the airport or train station and accompanies them to the accommodation;
 - it helps to decide and get acquainted with the important rules of being in this state;
 - answers all questions of guests and talks about objects that tourists meet and are interested in;
 - translates the local guide's story into the native language of the tour group;
 - helps to solve problems or difficulties;
 - helps in buying souvenirs and other things, translates menus in cafes and restaurants;
 - helps to fill out documents correctly when necessary in a foreign country.
- Tourists use the services of a guide-interpreter during the trip and, in addition to their main duties, are also responsible for their tour group:

- must be able to provide medical and psychological assistance;

- must explain to guests what to do.

A guide-interpreter should be a sufficiently active person with a broad outlook. His character is distinguished by his benevolence and participation in groups, and he should also know the place well and be able to adapt to any conditions accompanying the tour group. It effectively affects the sensitivity of information to guests, creates a positive mood in people and makes them fall in love with this corner of the world.

The more experienced the guide, the faster he understands the tourist group, because the guide-interpreter must quickly find an approach to customers. Rest and travel there will not last long.

The guide must create such an environment that the guest remembers this trip only positively and wants to return here after some time.

Tour companies should employ experienced guide-interpreters with excellent work experience. They have a license, so the services are officially provided. Our guides know the most interesting places and can create an interesting itinerary for a group of tourists.

If you've ever been abroad, you've probably come across tour guides. Popularly, representatives of this profession are called guides, but the duties of a guide-interpreter are much wider.

A guide-interpreter accompanies foreign tourists, introduces them to the customs and culture of the visited country, and also helps foreign guests to travel in an unfamiliar city.

Guide-interpreters must and must know the language of a group of tourists in a foreign country.

Working with foreign tourists brings a lot of impressions: the guide constantly meets new people, visits interesting places that office workers only dream of. This is a profession for active and open people. The main task of the guide is to introduce foreign guests to the city and the country, which is not as simple as it seems.

For successful work, a guide-interpreter must have the following qualities:

The guide-interpreter must know a foreign language well. In addition, the vocabulary of a professional guide is not limited to the vocabulary of historical, regional and everyday topics.

Modern tourists are very knowledgeable: guides often have to answer questions on the socio-economic, political agenda. Tourists need assistance in some matters other than excursions: emergency medical care or escort at a local specialty store, comprehensive and deep knowledge in the field of city and country history, art, architecture.

Many guides have a specialty: some guide tours of museums and galleries, some specialize in walking tours of the historic center, and some offer sightseeing tours.

Inside and out, guides know the history of the tourist site they specialize in. But every guide-interpreter should also be deeply immersed in the history of his country and city. The wider the worldview of the guide, the more valuable he is as an expert.

The guide-interpreter is the manager of the group, the curator of all the processes during the excursion. In addition to educational work, he deals with the transfer, food, accommodation, travel and excursion tickets and security of the group members.

These components of the tour are no less than the actual tour information: the overall impression and satisfaction of tourists from another day in a new country depends on whether the bus arrived on time, whether there were enough tickets for the session.

And if there are covers and problems during the tour, the guide cannot do without stress tolerance and impoliteness.

Conducting discussions and maintaining a positive mood of the group is a professional skill of the guide.

There are several ways to become a tour guide. The training of guide-interpreters is carried out at the faculties of translation, linguistics, and culture at additional educational programs, as well as at programs in "tourism", "excursion activities" and many other areas.

If there is no opportunity to get higher education, then guide-interpreters must take courses and get a certificate. Most programs and courses are held in Tashkent and Samarkand, but with the development of tourism in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, you can study as a guide in Bukhara, Khiva, Shakhrisabz, Karshi and other cities.

There are advantages and disadvantages to working as a tour guide.

Positive aspects:

- many office workers dream of traveling. Well, the guide-interpreter is often on the road and gets paid for it;
- every day the guide meets different people. And by communicating with interesting, curious tourists, it cheers up and gives energy;
- if the guide leads an excursion with a group of foreign tourists, he will have a great opportunity to get to know representatives of other cultures more deeply.

Disadvantages:

- seasonality;
- there is no limit of tourists in the high tourist season, for example, there is less work for guides in winter and autumn months;
- on your feet all day;
- the most of the time, guides spend the whole day with their tour group, they are not able to rest. This job requires tolerance.
- Main attractions are situated in large and resort cities, and there is almost no work for guide-interpreters in the regions.

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